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Eastern University, Sri Lanka,
Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University, India
and
ESN Publications, India**

23rd January 2024

Eastern University, Sri Lanka

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON PROMOTING GOOD HEALTH HABITS FOR CHILDREN (SPECIFIC TO 10 SELECTED YOUTUBE CHANNELS)

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ABSTRACT

Inculcating good health habits in every person is imperative, and the foundation for such habits should ideally be laid during childhood. Traditionally, young children learned these essential habits from their parents and other adults in their immediate environment. However, in today's digital age, the landscape has shifted, with social media playing a prominent role in shaping the behavior and choices of the young generation. Due to this, social media possesses significant potential in promoting social welfare and instilling virtuous values in children. The primary objective of this research is to investigate the role and effectiveness of Sinhala-language YouTube channels in facilitating the transmission and promotion of health habits among children. Qualitative research methodology was employed as the chosen approach to thoroughly investigate the nuanced aspects of how Sinhala YouTube channels contribute to the transmission of health habits among children. Primary data was collected through interviews with 20 randomly selected parents from Kandy Municipal Council. Additionally, content analysis was conducted on ten selected Sinhala language YouTube channels using secondary data sources. The channels selected for this research include Sinhala Fairy Tales, Cartoon Katha, Sinhala TV, Fairy World, Baby Hub, Siyasa Animations, Rupavahini Animation Studio, Tikiri Baba Animations, SL Animation Cartoon Hub, and Sinhala Kids Stories & Rhymes. The research conducted a content analysis of Sinhala YouTube channels, revealing a notable absence of health education content,

particularly related to fostering healthy habits. Instead, these channels predominantly featured other content types, overshadowing educational material. Interviews with parents reinforced this concern, highlighting that not only did these channels fail to reinforce healthy habits, but they could potentially undermine them. Commercial interests appeared to heavily influence the channel content, prioritizing views and engagement over informative, health-promoting material. This shift towards entertaining content often neglected to consider the developmental stages of children, risking potential misunderstanding or misinterpretation of health-related messages. Moreover, parents faced challenges in monitoring and filtering the content their children accessed on these channels, raising concerns about increased screen time and sedentary behavior. Children's prolonged engagement with these channels potentially replaced physical activities and outdoor play, prompting worries about the impact on their overall well-being. The researcher suggests that children's content creators on YouTube channels and parents need to be educated on this issue to make positive progress in children. Also, it is essential that content creators have a regulation or guidance when making content related to children.

KEYWORDS: Children, Good Health Habits, Influence, Promoting, Social Media.

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